

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
California State University, Los Angeles
Kaiser Permanente School of Anesthesia

EVALUATING ABORTION CARE QUALITY IN A CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY
STUDENT HEALTH CENTER

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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May 2024

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DOI 10.5281/zenodo.13738221

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: An unintended pregnancy is a pregnancy that was unwanted at the time of conception. In the United States (U.S.), there are 2.8 billion unintended pregnancies that occur annually and about half (40%) will result in an abortion. Medication abortion (MAB) is the most common type of in-person abortion that is 93-98% effective up to 77 days' gestation. With the passage of Senate Bill [SB] 24, also known as The College Student Right to Access Act (2023), California (CA) is the first state to ever require college student health centers (SHCs) to provide MAB services on campus. **Problem Statement:** Since MAB is a brand-new service to college SHCs in CA, there is very limited information that exists to assess the degree by which it improves patient and practice outcomes related to abortion care. **Purpose Statement:** The purpose of this project was to conduct a program evaluation of the MAB services provided at a college SHC in Los Angeles County, CA. **Theoretical Framework:** The Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA) Model was used as a framework. **Methods:** The project conducted a retrospective analysis of MAB patients' electronic health records at the SHC from January through December 2023. Outcome, process, and balancing measures were tracked. A patient satisfaction survey was also administered to assess the quality of MAB services and counseling received. **Results:** All of the MABs provided at the SHC were successful. There were no hospitalized adverse events or complications reported. Majority of the patients did not want to adopt a form of contraception after their MAB. There were no unnecessary clinic wait times. A good proportion of international students frequented the SHC for MAB services and accounted for unscheduled visits in between MAB appointments. **Discussion:** The project underscores the importance of evaluating a brand-new legislation and its profound impact on local college campuses in CA. SB 24 has significantly reduced the financial burden of pregnant college women who wanted an abortion. Contraceptive decision making, a comprehensive pain management regimen, and cultural considerations need to be addressed in the MAB patient education. **Recommendations:** Future recommendations include incorporating evidence-based strategies that support MAB patient education and contraceptive decision-making. Culturally-tailored interventions also need to be incorporated to reach the international student population that interact with the SHC for MAB services. Finally, a comprehensive pain management education is needed to adequately address the physical, emotional and psychological impact of going through an abortion process.

Key words: abortion, colleges, student health centers, reproductive health services, abortion quality metrics, abortion quality indicators

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The last two years were undoubtedly the most humbling years of my adult life. I want to thank God for keeping me steadfast, as I juggled a very rigorous doctoral program, while transitioning into a new job. I could not have produced a solid project, given the circumstances, without the guidance of Dr. Hannah Fraley and Dr. Laura Sarff. Thank you both for your leadership and expertise. Thank you to Dr. Rachel McClanahan for all the moral support. A very special thank you to Dr. Ederlina Landeta for believing in me during a time when I needed it the most.

I dedicate this achievement to my grandparents, Lolo Peping and Lola Susay. Thank you for teaching me to always aim for the stars. Your life lessons are with me, forever. Thank you to my parents, Ronald and Zeta, for your unconditional love and support throughout the years. Thank you to my sister, Iris, for always having my back. Thank you to my best friends for consistently being my anchor. Thank you to my Cohort 11 classmates, especially to Emma and Arianna, for being my cheerleaders during the times when the going got rough. I could not have done such a culminating feat without all of you.

Most of all, I dedicate this achievement to myself. I am in awe of the level of resilience, determination, and perseverance that I have displayed throughout a very challenging last two years. I am constantly in awe of my strength. Being a first-generation immigrant woman, I have learned to navigate the complexities of being bicultural mostly on my own. I am very proud of the woman that I have become and I look forward to the woman that I am becoming. I can do all things through Christ who strengthens me. Always.

Background

An unintended pregnancy is defined as a pregnancy that was not desired at the time of conception (Behonick, 2021). In the U.S., there are approximately 2.8 billion unintended pregnancies that occur annually, and about half (40%) of these pregnancies will result in abortion (Behonick, 2021; Raifman et al., 2018). Unintended pregnancies disproportionately affect women of color and low-income women who make 200% below the federal poverty line (Behonick, 2021; Finer & Zolna, 2016). In 2010, the U.S. spent an estimated \$21 billion in medical expenditures on poor maternal and infant outcomes associated with unintended pregnancies (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC], 2015).

Among women of reproductive age, the rates of unintended pregnancies are highest in ages 18 to 24 years, which correspond to college attendance (Finer & Zolna, 2016; Jordon & Ray, 2022; Oswalt et al., 2021). It is estimated that about 81 per 1,000 women ages 18-24 will have an unintended pregnancy and obtain about 42% of all abortions in the U.S. (Finer & Zolna, 2016; Guttmacher Institute, 2019a, 2019b; Raifman et al., 2018). Women who become pregnant while in college are 65% less likely to graduate compared to their non-pregnant counterparts (Jordon & Ray, 2022; Upadhyay et al., 2018). Similarly, 75% of pregnant college women who decide to continue their pregnancy will either drop out from at least one of their classes or drop out of school entirely, due to an inability to find childcare (Arhin & Cormier, 2008; Modrek et al., 2023; Jordon & Ray, 2022; Upadhyay et al., 2018). Women who were denied a wanted abortion are more likely going to develop economic hardship due to an inability to afford basic necessities, such as food, housing, and transportation for their families (Bixby Center for Global Reproductive Health, n.d.).

In the face of unintended pregnancies, having access to abortion services is therefore deemed essential (Behonick, 2021; Upadhyay et al., 2015). Women seek abortions for a myriad of reasons, including financial and timing-related concerns, not having the right partner, and a lack of mental and emotional preparedness to raise a child (Behonick, 2021; Biggs et al., 2013; Upadhyay et al., 2015). For college women, 89% report that having a child would negatively derail their educational trajectory and seek abortions to maintain a positive outlook for future aspirations (Modrek et al., 2023; Upadhyay et al., 2015, 2018). Many college women believe that having children while obtaining their degree would make it very difficult to achieve their educational, aspirational, and employment goals (Jaime et al., 2018; Upadhyay et al., 2018). Conversely, women who were denied a wanted abortion were found less likely to set aspirational life plans and more likely to feel hopeless about their future (McCarthy et al., 2018). Having access to abortion care, therefore, enables college women who are rifled with the possible consequences of unintended pregnancies an opportunity to attain academic success and complete their education (Baker & Mathis, 2022; Jaime et al., 2018; Upadhyay et al., 2018).

Current Legislation on Abortion Care in the U.S.

In June 2022, the U.S. Supreme Court (SCOTUS) overturned its landmark *Roe v. Wade* (1973) ruling, deferring the authority to individual states to decide on the legality of abortion and the conditions under which it can be performed (*Dobbs v. Jackson Women's Health Organization*, 2022). While several abortion bans now exist in other states across the U.S., abortion remains legal in CA. CA preserves the constitutional right to abortion and will continue to protect advanced practice clinicians who provide abortion services (Reproductive Right to Freedom Act, 2022). In November 2022, CA voters officially approved Proposition 1, which

includes the reproductive right to abortion in the CA State's Constitution (Reproductive Right to Freedom Act, 2022).

However, the fight to preserve abortion access in the U.S. continues. Less than one year after the SCOTUS decision to overturn *Roe v. Wade* (1973), an anti-abortion federal judge in Texas, Matthew J. Kacsmaryk, attempted to revoke the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA)'s 20-year approval of mifepristone, threatening access to MAB nationwide, even in CA where abortion is legal (*FDA v. Alliance for Hippocratic Medicine*, 2023). While U.S. President Joe Biden's administration issued an appeal to block this ruling, the U.S. Fifth Circuit Court of Appeals sustained the Texas decision, which rerouted the appeal to SCOTUS. As of April 24, 2023, SCOTUS issued a stay in *FDA v. Alliance for Hippocratic Medicine* (2023), preserving nationwide access to mifepristone.

Medication Abortion in California Public Universities

In 2017, there were approximately 132,680 abortions performed in CA, making up for 15.4% of the total abortions in the U.S. (Guttmacher Institute, 2022). Among college women attending CA's public universities, there is an estimated monthly total of 1,038 abortions, with an estimated 322-519 college women likely going to seek MAB (Upadhyay et al., 2018). MAB is currently approved by the U.S. FDA for use to terminate pregnancies up to 77 days' gestation (American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists [ACOG], 2020; Dzuba et al., 2020; Kapp et al., 2019; U.S. FDA, 2023). MAB consists of two medications: mifepristone and misoprostol. Mifepristone stops the pregnancy from growing, while misoprostol expels the pregnancy from the uterus (Dzuba et al., 2020). A standard MAB service typically requires two separate visits ranging between one to two weeks apart.

Although the majority of the abortions in the U.S. are primarily obtained from abortion facilities, about 36% are provided in primary care settings (Jones & Jerman, 2017). Women who receive abortion services from these settings report higher patient satisfaction given the privacy, trust, comfort, and convenience of being able to access their own primary care provider for such a sensitive service (Summit et al., 2016). SHCs in CA public universities serve as another trusted primary care setting that can provide abortion services to many college women (American College Health Association [ACHA], 2020; Baker & Mathis; 2022; Rohrer & Modrek, 2023). Raifman et al. (2018) concluded that all SHCs in CA already meet the minimum requirements to provide MAB services on campus, such as the physical space, adequate staffing, provision of pregnancy testing on-site, and pregnancy options counseling. However, it is noted that additional investment and funding are needed to arrange for security upgrades, after-hours services to triage MAB complications, referrals to local emergency departments, as well as provider training in managing unsuccessful abortions (Raifman et al., 2018).

Senate Bill 24: The College Student Right to Access Act

With the objective to promote social justice and equity in public education, Democratic CA State Senator Connie M. Leyva pioneered the re-introduction of SB 24 to the state legislature in 2019. SB 24, also known as The College Student Right to Access Act (2023), is the first ever senate bill to require SHCs across all CA's public universities to provide MAB services on campus (Legislative Counsel of California, 2019). SB 24 allocates \$200,000 to each CA public university to fund for upgrades necessary to safely provide MAB services on campus (Legislative Counsel of California, 2019; Raifman et al., 2018). On October 11, 2019, CA Governor Gavin Newsom officially signed SB 24 into law, making CA the first state to ever require public university SHCs to provide MAB services on campus effective January 3, 2023.

The provision of MAB services will be accomplished either through trained licensed staff on site, by telemedicine services, or via referrals to sub-contracted outside agencies (Legislative Counsel of California, 2019). As of January 3, 2023, MAB is now a reproductive care service that is offered across all 33 public universities in CA.

Statement of the Problem

The college SHC where this project took place just recently started providing MAB services on campus since January 3, 2023, per the SB 24 mandate. Prior to SB 24, pregnant college women on this campus who sought abortion services were referred to outside agencies, such as Family Planning Associates and Planned Parenthood Los Angeles. While these abortion facilities are conveniently located within a five-to-ten-mile radius from campus, the average cost for a MAB service is about \$750-800 out of pocket. Similarly, the average waiting time to schedule the earliest appointment is about seven days, with very limited weekend availability. As a result of the SB 24 mandate, the SHC now provides MAB services on campus for a reduced cost of \$78 in total. Although the SHC has an operational MAB protocol in place, it is a brand-new service with very limited information available to evaluate the degree by which it improves patient and practice outcomes specific to abortion care. To date, there is currently no method of evaluation that exists to assess the quality of abortion care that the SHC provides.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project was to conduct a program evaluation of the MAB services provided at this SHC. The specific aims of this project were: 1) to establish a baseline evaluation of the current program and its target population; 2) to identify opportunities for improvement; and 3) to improve practice and patient outcomes related to the provision of abortion care at the SHC.

Theoretical Framework

A theoretical framework provides the structure by which to conduct a quality improvement (QI) process. The theoretical framework chosen to facilitate and contextualize this DNP project is the Institute for Healthcare Improvement's PDSA Cycle. Originally developed by Walter A. Shewhart in 1924, the PDSA Cycle incorporates systems thinking and data analysis to create changes that will ultimately lead to process improvement (Best & Neuhauser, 2006).

The PDSA Cycle can be applied to a wide range of QI continuum and is used in many QI initiatives, from simple to more complex, faced in healthcare institutions (Langley et al., 2009; Provost & Murray, 2002). The PDSA cycle provides a framework to improve healthcare topics such as process workflows, patient satisfaction, provider satisfaction, and staff engagement (Allende-Richter et al., 2018; Kouo et al., 2020; Underwood et al., 2022). The PDSA Cycle has been a proven QI tool that guides process improvement, both in larger healthcare organizations and smaller primary care settings (Best & Neuhauser, 2006; Crowl et al., 2015; Gaudreault-Tremblay et al., 2020; Taylor et al., 2014).

Steps of the PDSA Cycle

The first step of the cycle, *Plan*, is to identify the objectives of the cycle and what needs to be changed. The second step, *Do*, is to implement the change. The third step, *Study*, is to analyze the data collected. Finally, the last step, *Act*, is to determine a plan of action if the results attained are not desirable (Appendix A) (Provost & Murray, 2020). The PDSA Cycle is an iterative process that can be repeated multiple times until desirable outcomes are achieved (Christoff, 2018; Langley et al., 2009).

Literature Review of the PDSA Cycle

The PDSA Cycle has been used in many healthcare settings to guide processes of change. The model has guided process improvement, both in larger healthcare organizations and smaller primary care settings (Best & Neuhauser, 2006; Crowl et al., 2015; Gaudreault-Tremblay et al., 2020; Taylor et al., 2014). James et al. (2022) used the PDSA cycle to pilot a mobility tech (MT) role in an inpatient acute care unit. In this project, the team ran one PDSA cycle to facilitate this test of change. The *Plan* involved a process mapping of the MT workflow in order to create a mobility protocol. The *Do* phase involved implementation of the MT role across all four acute care units. Data on mobility scores were collected and analyzed using run and control charts in the *Study* phase, which allowed the team to identify reasons why mobility interventions were not performed. Based on these results, the *Act* phase consisted of creating a standardized script that MTs can use to educate patients on the importance of mobility. Using the PDSA cycle, the team achieved overall their aim of improving mobility rates (James et al., 2022).

Mohamed et al. (2021) similarly adapted the PDSA Cycle to reduce morning hypoglycemia in children undergoing chemotherapy for acute lymphoblastic leukemia in an outpatient setting. The team conducted a series of PDSA cycles with one of the main interventions primarily geared towards caregiver education. The *Plan* was to assess caregiver knowledge on oral chemotherapy administration. The *Do* phase consisted of distributing surveys for caregivers to complete. The *Study* phase required analyzing the results of these surveys. Lastly, the *Act* phase involved creating a caregiver education bundle that addressed knowledge deficit and proper administration of oral chemotherapy. Using the PDSA Cycle, the project successfully decreased episodes of morning hypoglycemia in the two pediatric oncology clinics combined (Mohamed et al., 2021).

Multiple PDSA cycles can be implemented to allow for smaller-scale improvement efforts that can be adapted quickly, instead of larger-scale systemic changes that take a longer period of time (Henry et al., 2021; Langley et al., 2009; Venugopal et al., 2017). This provides opportunities for constant improvement by continually building upon knowledge from each cycle to support solutions that can be implemented into practice. Tabingo and Verzone (2020) aimed to increase the diabetes management compliance rate in an urban primary care clinic. This was achieved by conducting four PDSA cycles centered on team engagement, patient engagement, chart screenings, and by implementing a mnemonic bundle over an eight-week timeframe. As a result, the team was able to increase the diabetes management compliance rate by 72.2% at the end of the project's proposed timeframe (Tabingo & Verzone, 2020).

Using multiple smaller-scale PDSA cycles also allows teams to learn and reduce the likelihood of failure before changes are implemented on a wider scale (Provost & Murray, 2020). A DNP-led QI project similarly used multiple PDSA cycles to improve MAB follow-up rates in a high-volume, ambulatory, outpatient facility (Fagot, 2020). The project also ran four PDSA cycles to incorporate interventions related to staff and patient engagement, with an emphasis on a shared decision-making approach to MAB follow-up and birth control initiation after an abortion. As a result, the project increased MAB follow-up rates up to 84% via serum human chorionic gonadotropin testing compared to the overall follow-up rate of 52-73% using conventional in-clinic ultrasound methods (Fagot, 2020). Doing so, the project team hoped to alleviate the travel, cost, and scheduling barriers to abortion follow-up care.

The PDSA Cycle is a framework that is applicable to various QI processes in diverse healthcare settings. Given its success and viability in other healthcare settings, this DNP project

adapted the PDSA Cycle into the college SHC setting to facilitate a program evaluation on MAB services.

Adaptation of the PDSA Cycle in the SHC

The college SHC where this project took place just recently started providing MAB services on campus since January 3, 2023, per the SB 24 mandate. Although the SHC already has an operational MAB protocol in place, it is a brand-new service with very limited information available to evaluate the degree by which it improves patient and practice outcomes related to abortion care. The purpose of this DNP project was to conduct a program evaluation of the MAB services at the SHC, in order to improve practice and patient outcomes related to the provision of abortion care. In order to achieve this goal, this DNP project used the PDSA Cycle as a framework to guide the process of improvement (Appendix B).

Plan

The DNP Student/Team Leader (TL) conducted a literature review on abortion quality indicators and metrics used to evaluate abortion programs. The DNP TL then identified key stakeholders in the SHC, which included the SHC Director, SHC Assistant Director, one MAB provider, one Clinical Patient Health Educator (CPHE), one Senior Health Promotion Specialist (SHPS), and two Information Technology (IT) specialists. These stakeholders comprised the project team. The DNP TL also met with these stakeholders to discuss the project's objectives and implementation process.

Do

The DNP TL collected data using electronic health records and a pre-existing patient satisfaction survey. Data was collected retrospectively from patients who have received MAB

services at the SHC from January through December 2023. Data was extracted and stored in Microsoft Excel.

Study

After the data collection, the DNP TL analyzed the data and shared the results with the project team. Programs, such as Microsoft Excel, was used to assist with data analysis and presentation of results.

Act

The results of the data collection and analysis continued to guide the project team at the SHC to create revisions as needed in the MAB protocol, workflow, counseling, and other areas where improvement is indicated. Future PDSA cycles, if indicated, will be conducted outside of this project's scope and proposed timeline.

Plan for Literature Review

A comprehensive literature review was conducted in consultation with a California State University, Fullerton (CSUF) librarian in the following databases: PubMed and Cumulative Index to Nursing and Allied Health Literature (CINAHL). Key mesh terms included:

“abortion and students and colleges,” “abortion and student health center,” “college students and sexual health and religion,” “quality abortion metrics,” and “quality abortion indicators.”

Similar articles using the same mesh terms were scanned to identify pertinent studies. Reference lists of the articles were further handpicked to identify applicable publications.

The inclusion criteria for articles were: peer-reviewed, written in English, published in the U.S. only, and published between 2015 to 2023. Studies conducted outside the U.S. were excluded, as barriers and legislation regarding abortion access in other countries may be different. The focus of this paper was the in-clinic administration of MAB services, hence studies that included MABs administered via telemedicine, surgical abortions, and self-managed abortions were excluded. Guidelines on the provision of MAB services from ACOG, U.S. FDA, and Planned Parenthood Federation of America (PPFA) were also used as key references, as they provide relevant information on current practice guidelines related to MAB administration.

Literature Review

The literature review identified a total of 20 studies that were relevant to the project topic (Appendix C-E). Out of the 20 articles, four were systematic reviews (Chakraborty et al., 2022; Dennis et al., 2016; Filippi et al., 2020; Sorhaindo & Lavelanet, 2022), four observational studies (Anand et al., 2020; Baker & Mathis, 2022; Luquis et al., 2015; Martin et al., 2018), and twelve descriptive studies (Behonick, 2021; Bersamin et al., 2017; Homaifar et al., 2017; Jaime et al.,

2018; Jordan & Ray, 2023; Margo et al., 2016; Modrek et al., 2023; Oswalt et al., 2021, Rader et al., 2022; Raifman et al., 2018; Rohrer & Modrek, 2023; Upadhyay et al., 2018).

Key themes throughout the studies were identified and grouped according to three main categories: 1) patient barriers to abortion access, 2) provider barriers to abortion access, and 3) indicators of abortion care quality used to evaluate abortion programs. Within these categories, the social construct of abortion stigma was an overarching theme that is interwoven throughout the literature. The review of literature also noted various barriers to abortion access that support the need for the provision of quality abortion care in places where they are now accessible, such as college SHCs in CA. Implementation of standardized abortion quality measurement tools is therefore important in order to strengthen abortion services and maintain access to quality abortion care.

Since the provision of MAB services in college SHCs per the SB 24 mandate is a very recent legislation, there were limited studies identified in the literature. Majority of the studies were also of observational and descriptive design. Although observational and descriptive studies have a lower level of evidence (Grove & Gray, 2019), they provide a better understanding of student perspectives and the barriers they face in accessing abortion services. Five studies specifically explored access, socioeconomic, and psychosocial barriers to abortion services (Baker & Mathis, 2022; Bersamin et al., 2017; Jordon & Ray, 2022; Martin et al., 2018; Rohrer & Modrek, 2023). Four studies underscored the need for MAB services on college campuses (Behonick, 2021; Jaime et al., 2018; Raifman et al., 2018; Upadhyay et al., 2018). Three studies examined the current practices of abortion referrals and pregnancy options counseling in college settings (Anand et al., 2020; Modrek et al., 2023; Oswalt et al., 2021). Five studies explored the construct of abortion stigma and how it influences both patient and provider beliefs (Bersamin et

al., 2017; Margo et al., 2016; Homaifar et al., 2017; Sorhaindo & Lavelanet, 2022; Rohrer & Modrek, 2023). Lastly, three studies discussed the most recent research in abortion quality metrics pertinent to the development of a standardized method of evaluating abortion services (Dennis et al., 2016; Chakraborty et al., 2022; Filippi et al., 2020).

Medication Abortion

Unbiased pregnancy options counseling should include the discussion of all three options: to continue pregnancy, to refer for adoption, or to terminate the pregnancy (Oswalt et al., 2021). When a woman chooses to terminate pregnancy, she can do so via MAB or surgical abortion (TAB) depending on preference, gestational age eligibility, and state laws on abortion. MAB is proven to be 93-98% effective in terminating pregnancy up to 77 days' gestation, while TABs can be performed at any gestational age and is recommended for pregnancies greater than 77 days' gestation (Dzuba et al., 2020; PPFA, 2023). In CA, abortions can be performed up to the point of fetal viability, which is around 24 weeks of gestation (PPFA, 2023). Many women resort to MAB since it is less invasive, feels safer, and more natural. Others opt for TAB for a shorter and faster duration of treatment (ACOG, 2020; PPFA, 2023). A woman's choice rests on her personal preference and shared decision-making with her provider (Fagot, 2020).

In 2020, women in their twenties accounted for 57.2% of the 615,911 total abortions reported in the U.S. (CDC, 2022). Nearly all of the abortions (93.1%) performed were within the first trimester of pregnancy, with MABs accounting for more than half (54%) of all abortions in the U.S. (ACOG, 2020; CDC, 2022; Guttmacher Institute, 2022). Similarly, there is an estimated 322-519 MABs per month among University of California and California State University students combined, which is approximately 8-13 monthly MABs per 10,000 female students (Upadhyay et al., 2018). MAB is the most common type of abortion method that is administered

in-person and now increasingly via telemedicine to provide access for those who live in remote and rural areas (Jones et al., 2022; Modrek et al., 2023).

Pharmaco-physiology

MAB consists of two medications: mifepristone and misoprostol (ACOG, 2020). Mifepristone, also known as RU-486 or by its brand name Mifeprex, is a selective progesterone receptor modulator that acts as an anti-progesterone by binding to progesterone receptors in the uterus (ACOG, 2020; Kaiser Family Foundation [KFF], 2023). Mifepristone causes necrosis of decidua, softening of the cervix, and increases prostaglandin sensitivity and contractility of the uterus (ACOG, 2020). On the other hand, misoprostol is a prostaglandin E1 analogue that further softens the cervix and causes uterine contractions (ACOG, 2020; U.S. FDA, 2023). Both medications work in a synergistic effect to expel pregnancy tissue from the uterus (ACOG, 2020). Mifepristone 200mg is ingested orally first and depending on patient preference, misoprostol 800mcg is administered either buccally, orally, or vaginally 0-48 hours after (KFF, 2023). All forms are safe and equally effective (ACOG, 2020). In circumstances where mifepristone is unavailable, misoprostol-only administered up to three doses is an acceptable alternative regimen (ACOG, 2020; Raymond et al., 2023).

Side Effects

Heavy bleeding and cramping much similar to menses is expected. Nausea, vomiting, diarrhea, headache, fever, and chills are also common (Creinin et al., 2004, 2007; Schaff et al., 1999; Winikoff et al., 2008). Patients are normally given post-MAB bleeding precautions and counseled on signs and symptoms that would warrant urgent medical intervention (ACOG, 2020).

Follow-Up

MAB completion can be accomplished in three ways: at-home urine pregnancy testing, in-clinic ultrasound sonography, and serum Beta-hCG testing (Baiju et al., 2019; Chen et al., 2016; Fiala et al., 2003; Pocius et al., 2017). For patients who cannot return to the facility for follow-up, clinician phone assessment for resolution of pregnancy symptoms along with a negative at-home urine pregnancy test is recommended at least four weeks after MAB initiation (Baiju et al., 2019; Chen et al., 2016). Ultrasound sonography is also used to confirm absence of a gestational sac for patients who are able to return to the facility for follow-up (ACOG, 2020; Fiala et al., 2003). Lastly, patients can obtain serum Beta-hCG testing at a more convenient location if they cannot return to the facility. An 80% decrease from baseline levels at least one-week post-MAB indicates a successful abortion (Fiala et al., 2003; Pocius et al., 2017). Selecting the appropriate follow-up method is dependent on patient preference and should involve shared decision making between patients and their MAB provider (Fagot, 2020).

Complications

Complications of MABs include a failed abortion, incomplete abortion, excessive bleeding, and infection. The presence of prolonged bleeding, cramping, passing blood clots, and other continuing pregnancy symptoms, such as nausea, vomiting, breast tenderness, and fatigue warrants suspicion for a failed or incomplete abortion (ACOG, 2020; PPFA, 2023). A failed abortion can be treated with a repeat dose of misoprostol or via surgical aspiration; while an incomplete abortion can be treated with a repeat dose of misoprostol, surgical aspiration, or expectant management (ACOG, 2020). Retained pregnancy tissue from an incomplete abortion is also a risk factor for post-MAB endometritis. Endometritis is a uterine infection characterized by fever, chills, severe pelvic pain, and purulent, foul-smelling vaginal discharge (Meites et al.,

2010; Cohen et al., 2007). Generally, less than 1% of MAB patients will seek an emergency department visit for excessive bleeding and require blood transfusion (ACOG, 2020). The risk of uterine infections post-MAB is also uncommon (0.9%) and routinely using prophylactic antibiotics with MABs is not supported by current literature (ACOG, 2020).

Patient Barriers to Abortion Access

Access Barriers

Literature notes several access barriers to abortion care amongst pregnant college women. This includes cost of procuring the service, distance and travel time to the nearest abortion facility, lack of transportation, wait times, and limited appointment availability (Baker & Mathis, 2022; Rohrer & Modrek, 2023; Upadhyay et al., 2018). The average cost of a MAB service is about \$600-700 out of pocket, with the nearest abortion facility ranging between being one to six hours away from a college campus (Baker & Mathis, 2022; Rader et al., 2022; Upadhyay et al., 2018). MAB services are also rarely offered on the weekends and it usually takes up to seven days to schedule the first available appointment (Baker & Mathis, 2022; Upadhyay et al., 2018). Although these studies have an observational (Baker & Mathis, 2022; Upadhyay et al., 2018; Rader et al., 2022) and descriptive design (Rohrer & Modrek, 2023), which have a lower level of evidence (Grove & Gray, 2019), the findings provide understanding of the physical barriers that put pregnant college women at a higher risk of exceeding the gestational limit to be eligible for a MAB service.

In addition, a recent exploratory study also notes that only four percent of SHC websites actually advertise MAB services as being offered on campus or how students may access it (Modrek et al., 2023). The lack of information on these SHC websites erroneously sends a message that MABs are inaccessible or unsafe (Modrek et al., 2023). Although this study had a

large sample size and surveyed 547 public universities across the U.S., a limitation that was noted is that the study strictly examined websites only and not manual brochures on abortion services that could have been physically distributed to students. Nevertheless, the findings underscore that presenting information on abortion services is essential to support access.

Socioeconomic Barriers

There are also demographic and socioeconomic barriers prominent in abortion access. Jordon and Jay (2022) reports that colleges in poorer, low-income communities lacked access to abortion providers or had SHCs in general. These colleges were also noted to have a higher female enrollment compared to institutions that did have SHCs. Conversely, colleges from more affluent communities not only had SHCs on campus, but also had a lower percentage of multi-racial female enrollment (Jordon & Jay, 2022). These findings are similar to a study by Anand et al. (2020), which evaluated institutional characteristics that are associated with the type of abortion referrals. Colleges from higher levels of income were more likely to provide direct abortion referrals to appropriate resources, while those in poorer communities lacked access to any abortion resources in general (Anand et al., 2020). Furthermore, minority groups are also associated with lower levels of sexual and reproductive health knowledge, where White female students were generally more knowledgeable compared to their Hispanic female counterparts (Martin et al., 2018). Women from minority groups who have lower socioeconomic status are at a greater disadvantage in accessing abortion care; hence, findings from these studies should be considered when addressing reproductive justice and healthcare equity in abortion access. Even so, it is similarly important to highlight that all three of these studies used convenient sampling in recruiting their participants, which threatens external validity and affects the overall generalizability of the findings (Grove & Gray, 2019).

Psychosocial Barriers

One of the social constructs paramount to understanding psychosocial barriers to abortion access is stigma. Abortion stigma is defined as a negative quality that labels a woman inferior against the standards of womanhood based on the ideology that abortion is morally and socially wrong (Sorhaindo & Lavelanet, 2022). Several studies delineate that women refrain from seeking sexual and reproductive health services, including abortion care, due to concerns with privacy and confidentiality, social disapproval from family and friends, fear of judgment, denial, embarrassment, and shame (Bersamin et al., 2017; Rohrer & Modrek, 2023; Sorhaindo & Lavelanet, 2022). As a result, students may seek resources off-campus from pregnancy crisis centers that provide biased and non-factual information that dissuades women from obtaining an abortion altogether (Oswalt et al., 2021). Although these studies have a descriptive design (Bersamin et al., 2017; Rohrer & Modrek, 2023; Oswalt et al., 2021) and have a lower level of evidence, the findings further support the study by Sorhaindo and Lavelanet (2022), which is a systematic review that delineates how perceived stigma poses as a barrier to quality abortion care. Systematic reviews have the highest level of evidence and therefore reinforces applicability and generalizability of the findings into practice (Grove & Gray, 2019).

In order to further understand abortion stigma, it is also important to acknowledge the role of religiosity in shaping a woman's values, beliefs, and perception. For women who possess more conservative values, abortion is considered a sin that offends core spiritual principles (Sorhaindo & Lavelanet, 2022). Women who attend weekly religious services are also consistently associated with lower levels of sexual and reproductive health knowledge (Martin et al., 2018). While religion plays a protective role in delaying sexual activity, it is conversely correlated with decreased use of contraception, higher incidence of unprotected intercourse, and

therefore an increased risk of unintended pregnancies in college women (Luquis et al., 2015; Martin et al., 2018). Although Luquis et al. (2015) particularly examined Hispanic students only and therefore may not be applicable to other ethnic groups, the findings are comparable to those of Martin et al., (2018) and Sorhaindo and Lavelnet (2022). Together, these studies extrapolate how religiosity plays a significant role in shaping a woman's preconceived notions about sexual and reproductive health, which may further perpetuate the stigma associated with obtaining abortion care.

Provider and Staff Barriers to Abortion Access

The role of stigma and religiosity does not only pertain to abortion seekers, but equally shapes the perspectives of providers and medical staff who provide abortion services. SHCs in religious-affiliated institutions are less likely to provide comprehensive positive pregnancy test counseling and more likely to offer inappropriate abortion referrals to their students (Anand et al., 2020; Oswalt et al., 2021). Abortion seekers similarly report a lack of empathy, judgment, and insensitivity felt from providers when they sought out abortion services (Homaifar et al., 2017; Margo et al., 2016; Sorhaindo & Lavelanet, 2022). Likewise, many providers are also concerned of the criminal liability that is associated with providing abortion services (Sorhaindo & Lavelanet, 2022). As a result, fear of stigma and poor treatment from providers similarly lead abortion seekers to crisis pregnancy centers that overall discourage them from having an abortion altogether (Anand et al., 2020; Upadhyay et al., 2022). It is important to note that the studies by Anand et al., (2020), Homaifar et al., (2017), and Margo et al. (2016) were conducted in states outside CA, where abortion laws and provider perspectives may be different from those in CA. This is a noteworthy limitation that warrants cautious interpretation and applicability of the findings to the provision and receipt of abortion care in CA.

In addition, Oswald et al. (2021) examined college universities across the U.S. and further pinpoints regional differences between Southern and Midwestern states versus Western and Eastern states. Western and Eastern states have higher rates of comprehensive pregnancy all-options counseling compared to Southern and Midwestern states (Oswald et al., 2021). Faith-based institutions are also generally less likely to provide unbiased and comprehensive positive pregnancy options counseling compared to non-faith-based schools across the U.S (Oswald et al., 2021). Although Oswald et al. (2021) used self-reported surveys in the data collection, which are at risk for response bias and affect the overall generalizability of the findings (Grove & Gray, 2019), the study nevertheless signifies the role of religiosity in shaping stigma amongst abortion providers across the U.S.

ACOG and the American Academy of Family Physicians (AAFP) recommend that pregnancy test counseling be free of manipulation and coercion in order to preserve a woman's right to reproductive autonomy (ACOG, 2014, 2017; Oswald et al., 2021). Healthcare providers need to understand how their personal values may come into conflict with their professional responsibilities to provide unbiased abortion care (Cappiello et al., 2011; Oswald et al., 2021; Simmonds & Likis, 2005). In the event that a clinician is unwilling to provide abortion resources due to conflict in personal beliefs, it is recommended that an alternative clinician be available to provide comprehensive pregnancy all-options counseling rather than completely omitting it (AAFP, 2017; Oswald et al., 2021).

The Role of College Student Health Centers

With the ever-changing landscape of abortion care in the U.S., SHCs play an even more important role in the provision of abortion access to pregnant college women. With the passage of SB 24, CA is the first ever state to require public universities to provide abortion services on

campus (Legislative Counsel of California, 2019). SHCs are most frequently visited for sexual and reproductive health services and serve as a trusted source of information to many college students (ACHA, 2020; Baker & Mathis, 2022; Rohrer & Modrek, 2023). Literature shows that students are more likely to feel comfortable and experience less stigma accessing care at SHCs than they do at general primary care settings outside the college campus (Rohrer & Modrek, 2023). Raifman et al. (2018) also demonstrates that SHCs are already equipped with adequate physical space and staffing to provide MAB services on campus. The provision of MAB services at SHCs is expected to mitigate the barriers to abortion access, such as distance, travel, wait times, limited appointment availability, and the fear of stigma that may college women encounter when seeking abortion services off campus (Baker & Mathis, 2022; Upadhyay et al., 2018). Although these studies have an observational design and have a lower level of evidence (Grove & Gray, 2019), they elucidate the importance of providing MAB services on college campuses to enhance access to quality abortion care.

Evaluation of Abortion Programs

A program evaluation is a systematic review of a program's significance within a defined criterion (Yarbrough et al., 2011). Program evaluations consist of an investigation of the program's processes and outcomes, in order to understand how the program can be improved (Yarbrough et al., 2011). While SB 24 helps to ensure access to abortion services, provision of abortion care is more complex than what is required by the new legislation. The continued stigmatization of abortion, as well as the restrictive nature of providing and procuring abortion services, makes it difficult to capture abortion-related outcomes that are pertinent in program evaluations due to scarcity of data, lack of patient follow-up, and overall underreporting of abortion incidence (Darney et al., 2019). As a result, literature notes a lack of standardization in

abortion quality metrics to evaluate the quality of abortion programs (Dennis et al., 2016; Filippi et al., 2020).

Abortion Metrics Development

According to the World Health Organization, quality abortion care should be: “safe, timely, affordable, non-discriminatory, and respectful” (Abortion Service Quality Initiative, 2023). The CDC and U.S. Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality (AHRQ) have developed a criterion for quality metric development based on: importance, scientific soundness, and feasibility (Gavin et al., 2014; Remus & Fraser, 2004; Darney et al., 2019). Metric importance should highlight its relevance to stakeholders, meaning that improvements should directly alter clinical outcomes. Secondly, good quality metrics should also be scientifically sound, meaning that it produces valid and reliable results (Darney et al., 2019). Finally, metrics development should be feasible, meaning there is ease in data collection without undue burden or cost (Darney et al., 2019).

Standardization of Abortion Quality Metrics

Metrics and indicators are fundamental in abortion program evaluations, as they provide critical information on how services can be improved (Chakraborty et al., 2022; Filippi et al., 2020). To improve health outcomes in abortion care, several studies have worked to standardize the use of abortion quality metrics. Dennis et al. (2016) conducted a systematic review and identified 75 abortion indicators that primarily focused on abortion policies, systems and infrastructure, patient-provider interaction, decision making, as well as community resources and knowledge on abortion services. These indicators were categorized into domains and subthemes, and level of agreement in these indicators were also assessed. The main domains identified in the review were: structure, process, and outcomes indicators. Dennis et al. (2016) concluded that

there is very little consensus on what constitutes quality abortion care but noted that the bulk of abortion indicators focus on the process of abortion care provision. While strengths of this systematic review include evaluation of 13 peer-reviewed articles as well as grey literature, Dennis et al. (2016) notes a limitation that not all abortion indicators may have been captured when they were consolidated into categories and subthemes. Nevertheless, this systematic review provides the foundation for future studies to streamline abortion quality metrics in order to improve women's health outcomes and experiences with abortion care.

Filippi et al. (2020) elaborates on the work of Dennis et al. (2016) by conducting a scoping review of ten years' worth of published abortion literature from 2008 to 2018, in order to provide an extensive summary of abortion quality metrics. Filippi et al. (2020) extracted a total of 792 indicators from 142 peer-reviewed articles and categorized them into seven primary domains. Similar to the findings of Dennis et al. (2016), Filippi et al. (2020) notes that the majority of abortion indicators focus on the process of providing abortion care. Filippi et al. (2020) further details how these indicators were extracted, namely through health provider surveys, client exit interviews, facility assessment surveys, population surveys, as well as prospective analyses of medical health records to assess abortion-related morbidity events. Although Filippi et al. (2020)'s review is broader in scope compared to Dennis et al. (2016), it was noted that it was impossible to assess the validity and reliability of these indicators due to the extensive number of indicators extracted. Despite these limitations, Filippi et al. (2020) provides a wide breadth of abortion metrics that can be used as a starting point for many abortion programs to develop their own data collection tailored to their own objectives.

The most recent research on abortion quality metrics was conducted by Chakraborty et al. (2022). Chakraborty et al. (2022), also known as the ASQ Initiative, are representatives from

Metrics for Management, Ipas, and Ibis Reproductive Health, which are global non-profit organizations committed to enhancing access to quality reproductive and abortion care worldwide. Chakraborty et al. (2022) aimed to build upon the work of Dennis et al. (2016) to standardize abortion quality metrics and examined 1,860 abortion quality indicators from 12 abortion service organizations. Similar to the findings of Dennis et al. (2016) and Filippi et al. (2020), 75% of these indicators also focused on process measures. These indicators were assessed against abortion outcomes that measure both clinical and patient experiences with abortion care and were field-tested in three countries to further ensure feasibility and generalizability. However, there are several limitations in the Chakraborty et al. (2022) study. Due to a lengthy four-year study, there was attrition among research team participants, which may have impacted their overall understanding of the research aims. Although there was an extensive number of indicators examined, it is also possible that they may not be representative of all pregnant women seeking abortion care (Chakraborty et al., 2022). Nevertheless, results of the study created a process by which abortion metrics can be evaluated and ultimately led to the development of the Abortion Care Quality (ACQ) Tool. The ACQ Tool is the first ever global standardized measurement tool that can be used to assess the quality of abortion care. The ACQ Tool consists of a site checklist, provider survey, and patient satisfaction surveys that are free for use to evaluate abortion programs worldwide (Abortion Service Quality Initiative, 2023).

The studies by Dennis et al. (2016), Filippi et al. (2020), and Chakraborty et al. (2022) are all systematic reviews that represent the most recent research on abortion quality metrics. Systematic reviews involve a very thorough and comprehensive synthesis of current literature that can best address a healthcare problem (Grove & Gray, 2019). Systematic reviews represent the highest level of evidence used for developing clinical practice guidelines in patient care,

which in this case, is the standardization of metrics that can be used to evaluate the quality of abortion care (Grove and Gray, 2019).

Tools for Data Collection

Electronic Health Records. Electronic health records are an important source of patient information that can be used for data collection in quality improvement and program evaluations (Alzu'bi et al., 2021). In the Filippi et al. (2020) study, electronic health records were used to extract patient demographic characteristics that are pertinent in abortion program evaluations, such as: age, race/ethnicity, level of education, type of insurance coverage, parity, and gestational age at the time of abortion. Electronic health records are similarly used to prospectively analyze abortion-related morbidity events, such as infection, incomplete abortions, post-abortion complications, and the psychological well-being of women who sought abortion services (Filippi et al., 2020). Several studies have also used electronic health records to assess abortion incidence and prevalence, all of which are important outcome indicators used to evaluate abortion programs (Filippi et al., 2020).

Client Exit Interviews. Client exit interviews are the most commonly used data source to assess the quality of abortion care provision (Filippi et al., 2020). Women's satisfaction with abortion care is operationalized by measuring the perceived level of trust, privacy, confidentiality, and respect with the abortion provider and staff during their visit (Filippi et al., 2020). Abortion outcomes that focus on the emotional and psychological well-being of women after receiving abortion services are also operationalized by measuring level of anxiety, relief, empowerment, depression, shame, and guilt (Filippi et al., 2020). These indicators of abortion quality are often extracted using client exit interview surveys administered after receiving abortion services (Filippi et al., 2020). Filippi et al. (2020) has provided an extensive list of

abortion quality indicators and outcomes that can be tailored according to an organization's objectives in conducting evaluations of their abortion services.

Summary

There are several physical, socioeconomic, and psychosocial barriers to abortion access that equally affect abortion seekers and abortion providers. Existence of these barriers support the need for MAB services to be provided on college campuses, as outlined by the recent SB 24. College SHCs play a very important role in helping mitigate the barriers to abortion access amongst pregnant college women. In providing abortion services, however, it is important for stakeholders to understand what constitutes quality abortion care. Several studies suggest that health outcomes related to abortion care are difficult to quantify due to scarcity of abortion data and a lack of standardization of abortion quality metrics, which directly results from the continued stigmatization of seeking and providing abortion services. Process improvement initiatives geared towards improving the quality of abortion care should therefore evaluate process measures that link abortion quality indicators with abortion outcomes.

Developing a standardized way to evaluate abortion metrics is essential, in order for stakeholders to understand how to strengthen their abortion programs. All pregnant women should receive the same level of quality abortion care, regardless of where it is obtained (Chakraborty et al., 2022). Understanding how to measure the abortion care quality is a valuable tool in the processes of evaluation that are pertinent both in small and large abortion service organizations. Therefore, conducting a program evaluation of the MAB services that are brand-new to CA's college SHCs is critical in order to enhance access to quality abortion care among pregnant college women.

Methods

The college SHC where this project took place just recently began providing MAB services on campus since January 3, 2023, per the SB 24 mandate. Although the SHC has an operational MAB protocol and workflow in place, the MAB program is a brand-new service and very limited information is available to evaluate the degree by which it improves patient and practice outcomes related to abortion care. To date, there is no method of evaluation that exists to assess the quality of abortion care provided. The purpose of this DNP project was to therefore conduct a program evaluation of the MAB services offered at the SHC.

Setting

This DNP project took place in a college SHC in Los Angeles County, CA. This SHC provides a wide breadth of healthcare services, including primary care, sexual and reproductive care, sports medicine, chiropractic medicine, internal medicine, acupuncture, and optometry services. As of Fall 2022 enrollment, the college campus where this SHC is located serves a total of 36,123 students, where 19,867 (55%) are female and 16,164 (45%) are male. This college campus also has a very ethnically diverse composition, with 20,039 (55%) Hispanic students, followed by 7,237 (20%) Caucasian, 3,315 (0.9%) Asian, and 1,699 (0.5%) Black/African American students. There are 70% first-generation students on campus, while 30% are continuing generation students. A majority of the students are pursuing baccalaureate degrees (89%), with a small percentage pursuing graduate study (11%).

Participants

Participants for this project included the SHC Director, SHC Assistant Director, one MAB provider, one CPHE, one SHPS, and two IT specialists. The DNP Student who conducted this project is one of the designated MAB providers and participated in all aspects of the project

as the TL. All of these participants each had an essential role in implementing the project. For example, the SHC Director is responsible for the administrative oversight in the SHC. The SHC Assistant Director and SHPS help conduct health promotion assessments in the SHC and on campus. The CPHE provides an extensive positive pregnancy test all-options counseling with students and facilitates referrals to abortion facilities as needed. The MAB provider assesses MAB eligibility, prescribes the medications, facilitates MAB education and counseling, and evaluates abortion completion at the follow-up visit. Finally, the IT specialists aid in extracting pertinent information from the SHC's electronic health records.

Ethical Considerations

Approval from the institutional review board (IRB) was obtained from CSUF and California State University, Northridge (CSUN) (Appendix U-V). The DNP TL also obtained a letter of support from the SHC Director (Appendix T) prior to implementing the project and confidentiality was maintained. De-identified data was stored in an Excel file on the DNP TL's password protected computer with Apple FileVault software and stored in her locked office at the project site. Data was analyzed in aggregate form.

Project Design

The project design was a program evaluation using a mixed methods design. Mixed methods combine both quantitative and qualitative data collection in a single study (Grove & Gray, 2019). This project involved a retrospective data collection and analysis of MAB services rendered from January 2023 through December 2023. Quantitative and qualitative data was collected and analyzed. The PDSA Cycle was used as a framework to facilitate the process.

Plan

The DNP TL/MAB provider met with the project team, which included the SHC Director, SHC Assistant Director, CPHE, SHPS, and IT specialists to discuss the project plan. The program evaluation consisted of a retrospective data analysis of MAB patient charts seen at the SHC from January through December 2023, as well as a patient satisfaction survey administered post-MAB.

Do

The DNP TL evaluated the MAB program in two ways: 1) conducting a comprehensive review of patient demographic data, as well as outcome, process, and balancing measures specific to abortion care, which were extracted from the SHC's electronic health records; and 2) an assessment of MAB counseling using a patient satisfaction survey following receipt of MAB services at the SHC. Data was collected retrospectively for MAB patients seen at the SHC from January through December 2023. Patient satisfaction surveys were administered through a telephone survey by the SHC's CPHE. A maximum of two call attempts were made. Patients who elected to participate provided consent and were notified that they can withdraw at any time. De-identified quality metrics data were abstracted and inputted into Microsoft Excel. Patient survey data were de-identified and stored in Excel file format for aggregate analysis.

Study

After the data collection, the DNP TL manually analyzed the data. Results were analyzed using descriptive statistics, such as means, percentages, and count data.

Act

This program evaluation project established a baseline understanding of where the SHC's MAB program currently stands. These results continued to guide the project team at the SHC to

create revisions as needed in the MAB protocol, workflow, counseling, and other areas where improvement is indicated. Future PDSA cycles, if indicated, will be conducted outside of this project's scope and proposed timeline.

Data Collection

The data collection tools chosen to extract pertinent information for this project were electronic health records and patient satisfaction surveys for patients who received MAB services at the SHC from January through December 2023.

Electronic Medical Records

The DNP TL tracked available patient demographics of MAB patients seen at the SHC: age, race/ethnicity, gender, academic year, health insurance coverage, parity, and gestational age, pre- and post-MAB contraception. These demographic characteristics were chosen as they are pertinent in understanding the target population in many abortion program evaluations (Filippi et al., 2020). Data extraction was retrospectively conducted for MAB patients who were seen from January through December 2023. This information was manually extracted using a table (Appendix R) and corresponding data was stored in Microsoft Excel file format.

Patient Satisfaction Survey

Prior to SB 24, the SHC already had a pre-existing services evaluation survey that was used to assess patient satisfaction with referrals to nearby abortion facilities. Since the SHC now provides MAB services on campus, this services evaluation survey was modified in collaboration with the SHC project team by adding items from the ACQ Tool's client exit interview survey that are specifically tailored to what is pertinent in the SHC setting (Abortion Service Quality Initiative, 2023; Charkraborty et al., 2022). The newly modified patient satisfaction survey was a seven-item questionnaire that contains four dichotomous yes or no response items, two Likert-

type scale items, and one open-ended question (Appendix B). Responses were analyzed in aggregate form and key themes were extracted from the open-ended question item.

Since this survey was finalized in July 2023, the project team decided to administer only to patients who were seen from July through December 2023. IRB approvals were also obtained from CSUF and CSUN during this timeframe. Patient satisfaction surveys were administered by a telephone survey. A maximum of two call attempts were made. Patients who elected to complete the patient satisfaction survey provided consent to participate and were informed that they can withdraw at any time. No identifying information was collected and data was analyzed in aggregate form.

Operational Definitions. Perception is defined as an individual's ability to create and interpret meaning from various psychological stimuli (Tacca, 2011). In this project, the patient satisfaction surveys measured pregnant college women's perceived level of understanding, preparedness if complications occur, and respect felt from staff throughout their MAB visit. These are all indicators of quality abortion care deemed important by the ASQ Initiative (Chakraborty et al., 2022). Level of perception for each of these abortion quality indicators were operationalized using a dichotomous yes or no response format. For example, for perceived level of understanding, the survey evaluated whether the MAB provider checked to make sure all the information provided was understood using a yes or no response. Similarly, for perceived level of preparedness if complications occur, the survey evaluated whether the patient understands what complications to look out for using a yes or no response. Each dichotomous question response item had a section for additional comments if patients wished to elaborate on their responses. Key themes were extracted and analyzed from these open-ended comments sections.

In addition, question items on pain management effectiveness and overall satisfaction with the care received were operationalized using a three and four-point Likert type scale, respectively (Grove & Gray, 2019). Likert scales are commonly used to measure opinions of project participants (Grove & Gray, 2019). Effectiveness of pain management was evaluated if it was very effective, somewhat effective, or not effective. Overall satisfaction with the care received during the MAB visit were evaluated as being excellent, good, adequate, or poor. Each of these response categories was assigned a value for data collection and analysis (Grove & Gray, 2019).

Measures

In facilitating a quality improvement process, measures are essential to evaluate the impact of a proposed change. Multiple measures are indicated in order to assess various aspects of the project within a system (Provost & Murray, 2020).

Outcome Measures

Outcome measures demonstrate that a change has led to an improvement and having at least one outcome measure is necessary (Provost & Murray, 2020). The outcome measures chosen for this project were: 1) the proportion of MABs that were complete, incomplete, and failed MABs; 2) proportion of abortion-related adverse events that were hospitalized; and 3) the proportion of patients who adopted a post-MAB method of contraception (Filippi et al., 2020). Adverse events are defined as prolonged heavy bleeding, nausea, vomiting, fever, chills, and severe pain that necessitated a hospital referral. Abortion completion, adverse events that measure cause-specific morbidity events, and post-MAB contraception are all important abortion outcomes identified in the Filippi et al. (2020) study.

$$\text{Outcome Measure 1} = \frac{\text{complete, incomplete, failed MAB}}{\text{total number of MABs}}$$

$$\text{Outcome Measure 2} = \frac{\text{number of abortion-related adverse events that were hospitalized}}{\text{total number of adverse events}}$$

$$\text{Outcome Measure 3} = \frac{\text{number of patients who adopted a post-MAB method of contraception}}{\text{total number of patients}}$$

Process Measures

Process measures are directly linked to outcome measures and will usually show improvement first. Process measures are a good indication of whether the proposed changes will influence the outcome measures (Provost & Murray, 2020). The process measures chosen for this project were: 1) the time spent with the MAB provider over the total time spent in the clinic; and 2) number of MAB patients who reported contacting FoneMed over the total number of MAB patients. FoneMed is an after-hours service line that the SHC contracted to help facilitate triage MAB complications and emergency department referrals during after-hours. Total time spent for MAB counseling and contacting the designated number for help provide a good assessment of the process of abortion care provision (Filippi et al., 2020).

$$\text{Process Measure \#1} = \frac{\text{time spent with MAB provider}}{\text{total time spent in clinic}}$$

$$\text{Process Measure \#2} = \frac{\text{number of MAB patients who reported contacting FoneMed}}{\text{total number of MAB patients}}$$

Balancing Measures

Finally, balancing measures help to identify unwanted consequences that result from a process change. Balancing measures can also provide another explanation for the improvement (Provost & Murray, 2020). The balancing measure chosen for this project is the proportion of MAB patients who returned for an unscheduled visit over the total number of MAB visits. Returning for an unscheduled visit means the patient did not understand what was discussed during MAB counseling and is also a good assessment of the process of abortion care provision (Filippi et al., 2020).

$$\text{Balancing Measure \#1} = \frac{\text{number of MAB patients who returned for an unscheduled visit}}{\text{total number of MAB patients}}$$

Analysis/ Evaluation

Data was stored in Microsoft Excel and was analyzed using the QI Macros statistical software program. Results were analyzed using descriptive statistics, such as means, percentages, and count data. For the open-ended questions in the patient satisfaction survey, common themes were identified using basic qualitative descriptions. Results were displayed using tables and bar graphs. These results will then be shared with the project team and areas of improvement will be discussed. Future PDSA cycles will then be initiated as needed.

Project Timeline

The timeline for this DNP project was detailed in Appendix F. The application for IRB approval was submitted in September 2023. Once IRB approvals were obtained, data collection started as early as September 2023 and continued through December 2023. Once data collection was completed, the DNP student analyzed the results and shared with the project team. These steps followed the PDSA Cycle framework used to facilitate this project.

Expected Outcomes

The SHC MAB program did not have a formal process to evaluate overall quality nor track outcomes related to abortion care prior to this project. The expected outcomes of this DNP project were to establish the SHC's baseline MAB program care quality. Results of the data collection and analysis guided the project team at the SHC to make revisions as needed in the MAB protocol, workflow, counseling, and other areas where improvement is indicated.

Results

From January through December 2023, the SHC scheduled a total of 14 MAB appointments. Out of the 14 appointments, there was one no-show, one patient that was actually not pregnant upon confirmation with a negative urine pregnancy test in clinic, and the last patient who decided to continue pregnancy right after her MAB visit. Overall, there were a total of 11 patients who received MAB services from the SHC (N=11) and completed the MAB process from start to finish.

Demographic Data

Patients who received MAB services from the SHC ranged in age from 17 to 29 years, with an average age of 22. The MAB patients had a diverse ethnic composition, with most of the patients from Hispanic descent (45%). Majority of the patients (82%) are pursuing a Bachelor's Degree, while 18% are pursuing Graduate studies. The patients who are pursuing Graduate studies are both international students from India. Majority of the patients (55%) did not have health insurance coverage documented in the chart at the time of their MAB visit, 27% had Family Planning, Access, Care, Treatment (PACT) coverage, and 9% had outside insurance. In terms of gestational age, all of the patients (100%) were in the first trimester of pregnancy, ranging from 3.6 to 7.3 weeks gestation determined either per their last menstrual cycle or via ultrasound sonography as indicated. All of the patients (100%) were also nulliparous, meaning it was their first time being pregnant, prior to their MAB visit. All but one patient (91%) were not on any form of birth control method prior to becoming pregnant. The one patient who was on a birth control method was on combined oral contraceptive pills, but reported not taking it consistently at the time of conception. Details on the demographic data collected are outlined in Appendix G.

Measures

Out of the 11 MAB patients, there were two patients that were lost to follow up. These patients were therefore not assessed for MAB completion, as well as adverse events and concerns that may have occurred during their MAB process.

Outcome Measures

Out of the patients that did come back for their MAB follow up visit (N=9), all had a successful and complete MAB (100%). None of the patients (0%) also reported any hospitalized adverse events during their MAB. Lastly, 89% of the patients who completed their MAB did not want to start on any form of contraception after their MAB. The one patient that did opt to start on combined oral contraceptives after her MAB never took them as prescribed and became pregnant again shortly after (Appendix H-K). Although it is not an outcome measured within the scope of this project, the subsequent pregnancy was miscarried and the patient was diagnosed with an incomplete, spontaneous abortion.

Process Measures

The average time that each patient spent with the MAB provider (N=11) was 85.8 minutes. This number was determined by subtracting the time each patient was ready for the MAB provider from the time that they were checked out from the clinic. The average total time that each patient spent in the clinic (N=11) was 88.3 minutes. This number was determined by subtracting the time that each patient checked in for their MAB visit from the time that each patient was checked out from the clinic. Given these results, patients spent 97% of their time on average with the MAB provider over the total time they spent in the clinic (Appendix L-M).

Out of the nine patients that did come back for the MAB follow-up appointment, none of them (0%) reported calling the after-hours triage line, FoneMed, for any urgent concerns during their MAB process (Appendix N-O).

Balancing Measures

Out of the 11 patients that received MAB services from the SHC, there were two (18%) that had unscheduled visits in between their initial MAB and follow-up appointment. One of these visits was an in-person clinic visit with the concern of possible excessive bleeding during their MAB process, while the other was a telephone visit with the concern of not having enough bleeding as expected during their MAB process (Appendix P-Q).

Patient Satisfaction Survey

The patient satisfaction survey was finalized by the project team at the end of June 2023. It was set to be distributed to patients who had received MAB services from the beginning of July 2023 to present. The project team collectively decided that the post-MAB surveys be conducted by the CPHE via a telephone call one week after their MAB follow-up visit. Patients that were seen at the beginning of the year (from January through June 2023) will not receive the post-MAB surveys, as it already had been a significant amount of time elapsed since their initial MAB visit. The project team decided on this survey time-frame to collect a more timely and accurate assessment of the MAB patients' experience. Since the scope of this DNP project is only evaluating patients who had received MAB services at the SHC from January through December 2023, there were only four patients that were eligible for the survey time-frame that was determined by the project team. Out of the four patients (N=4), only one patient agreed to participate and the rest either did not answer the phone or chose to not participate altogether.

The one patient who opted to participate in the post-MAB telephone survey rated the overall care that she received as “good” on the 4-point Likert scale question item and further commented that her MAB process “went well.” The patient also reported that the clinician provided information and answered her questions in a non-judgemental, respectful, and unbiased way. Moreover, the patient denotes that the clinician used easy-to-understand words and phrases, and made sure she understood all the information that was provided by “giving her handouts.” The patient also reports that the clinician explained possible complications related to the medication. However, when assessed if the pain medication she was given was effective, the patient notes that it was only “somewhat effective” on the 3-point Likert scale question item. Finally, the patient shared that she will “come back for birth control later when [she] is ready.”

Discussion

The results of this DNP project underscore the importance of evaluating a policy change, whether it is a local or state level legislation. SB 24, or The College Student Right to Access Act (2023), was implemented to help mitigate the barriers to abortion access amongst pregnant college women in CA, including cost, travel, and scheduling availabilities of MAB services (Baker & Mathis, 2022; Rohrer & Modrek, 2023; Upadhyay et al., 2018). Majority of the patients who received MAB services from the SHC did not have health insurance coverage at the time of visit and would have had to pay roughly \$600-700 out of pocket expenses for MAB services off campus (Baker & Mathis, 2022; Rader et al., 2022; Upadhyay et al., 2018). As a result of SB 24, the SHC was able to provide MAB services to these patients on campus at a significantly reduced cost of \$77 in total for all the medications. College students already have limited financial means and SB 24 has been a tremendous aid in this regard.

Another finding also worth noting is the handful of international students from India that procured MAB services from the SHC. Interestingly, these students also accounted for the unscheduled visits in between their initial MAB and follow-up visits, riddled with questions regarding expected bleeding patterns during and even after the MAB. These patients moreover had overwhelming concerns of privacy and confidentiality, fearing that their families will have access to their medical records. While it is not an outcome measured within the scope of this project, one of these patients medically withdrew from classes as a result of the MAB process interfering with her ability to concentrate on her studies. By the same token, it was also one of these patients who opted for a birth control method post-MAB, but was not taking it as prescribed and became pregnant again just shortly after as a result.

As of Fall 2022 enrollment, international students comprise 3.4% of the total student population on this college campus and a large number of these students frequent the SHC for basic primary care services. While the legality of safe abortion remains a controversial topic in the U.S., it is deemed even more taboo in third-world countries, like India, where 95% of women remain unaware of the legal conditions by which safe abortion methods can be procured in the first place (Choudhuri, 2022). This finding poses cultural considerations when providing MAB services to these patients and is an area of future study where culturally-sensitive education can be implemented at this SHC.

Another area of counseling that can also be highlighted during the initial MAB visit is pain management. The same patient who withdrew from her classes as a result of her MAB reported that her pain management regimen was only “somewhat effective.” Appropriate management of pain is an indicator of high quality abortion care and should address not just physical pain, but also the emotional and psychological aspects that are associated with the abortion process (Qian et al., 2023). Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs are recommended as the mainstay treatment to help manage the cramping during an abortion (Reynolds-Wright et al., 2022). However, literature also suggests non-pharmacological modalities that can help decrease the discomfort through the expected abortion pain and bleeding. These include the use of heating pads to the lower pelvis, uterine fundal massage, as well as being around a supportive environment during the process (Ipas Reproductive Health, 2022). Other studies recommend the use of psychological interventions, such as the use of encouraging language, deep breathing techniques, and music therapy to reduce abortion pain (Qian et al., 2023). The quality of education and care that women receive during an abortion directly impacts their ability to cope with a traumatic experience, which in turn shapes their long-term psychological well being (Qian

et al., 2023). These are all important counseling points that can moreover be included in the comprehensive, culturally-sensitive, patient education during and after the MAB visit.

While it is not surprising that the majority of MAB patients were not on any form of contraception at the time of conception, it was alarming to learn that 89% of the patients did not want to adopt a contraceptive method after the abortion. Women who do not initiate contraception after an abortion are significantly more likely to have a repeated unintended pregnancy within a year of the abortion (Postlethwaite et al., 2018). Literature suggests that initiating hormonal contraception even as early as the day of Mifepristone administration does not affect the effectiveness of the MAB (Kim et al., 2021). Other studies report that patients who adopt long-acting reversible contraception (LARC) immediately after an abortion are less likely to have a repeated unintended pregnancy than those who only had a short-acting birth control method or no contraception at all (Postlewaite et al., 2018). More importantly, as in the case of the majority of this DNP project's patient population, nulliparous women under the age of 26 years are also positively associated with LARC uptake post-abortion (Dixon et al., 2022) and should also be a central focus of the education that occurs during the MAB follow-up visit. As such, a patient-centered approach that includes individual priorities and goals should be utilized in the contraceptive counseling to mitigate provider coercion and therefore preserve high quality abortion care (Pearlman et al., 2023).

The low turnout in patient satisfaction surveys was also not surprising and expectedly echoes the findings of several studies. Darney et al. (2019) delineates that capturing abortion-related outcomes is often difficult due to lack of patient follow-up and therefore contributing to the scarcity of available abortion data that could help standardize quality abortion care (Dennis et al., 2016; Filippi et al., 2020). Abortion continues to be a taboo subject and patients are reluctant

to participate in abortion care-related satisfaction surveys, as was in the case of this DNP project, for fear of having to relive the experience. Several studies have recommended focusing on structural and process measures instead to evaluate the quality of abortion care (Dennis et al., 2016; Filippi et al., 2020).

Despite these challenges, this DNP project determined that the current MAB workflow at the SHC is successful as evidenced by results of the outcome and process measures. Patients spent the bulk of their time with the MAB provider over their total time spent in the clinic, which implies that there were no unnecessary wait times or flow stoppers at the front of the clinic. According to Filippi et al. (2020), abortion facility wait time is an excellent predictor of abortion care quality and that was well evident in this project. Furthermore, there were no hospitalized adverse events reported and patients also did not report using the after-hours triage line, FoneMed, for any urgent concerns outside clinic hours. These metrics are representative of the quality education provided by the MAB providers in the SHC, which is similarly reinforced by the positive responses on the patient satisfaction survey that the project was able to collect. Most importantly, all of the MABs that were performed at the SHC were successful and there were no complications reported that necessitated further medical intervention. These are all metrics discussed in the literature that adequately measure quality abortion care (Dennis et al., 2016; Filippi et al., 2020).

Limitations

Several limitations need to be accounted for when interpreting the results of this project. Since SB24 is a very recent state legislation and MAB is a brand-new service in CA college campuses, this DNP project had a very small sample size. The DNP project team also collectively decided on a patient satisfaction survey time-frame that was not able to capture the

experience of MAB patients that received services from the SHC from January through June 2023, which may have contributed to the low survey eligibility and turnout. While these limitations reduce the overall generalizability of the findings, they nevertheless reinforce the importance of SB24 and the provision of MAB services on college campuses. The findings of this project serve as a foundation for future research to elaborate on, such as the implementation of culturally-sensitive education materials for international students that frequent the SHC for basic sexual and reproductive health services.

Conclusion

To this day, abortion remains a controversial subject that many continue to avert. However, this DNP project was able to evaluate a brand-new state legislation and its long-lasting impact on local college campuses in CA. The advent of SB 24 in CA underscores the importance of evaluating a policy change that not only safeguards legal access to abortion care, but pioneers the fight to preserve reproductive justice for all women.

Future recommendations include continuing to conduct PDSA cycles to evaluate the new MAB program at a CA college campus and to revise the program based on continued study findings. It is moreover recommended that future quality improvement work focus on implementing and evaluating evidence based strategies that support MAB patient education and follow-up regarding contraception decision-making. Finally, future work should prioritize incorporating culturally-tailored interventions to reach the international student population who may interact with the college health center for MAB services, as well as adequately address the physical, emotional, and psychological impact of an abortion process.

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Appendix A

Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA) Cycle

Appendix B

Adaptation of the PDSA Cycle in the SHC

Appendix C

Table of Evidence for Literature Review

Database: PubMed

Search Terms	Limits	Articles retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
Abortion and students and colleges	Peer-reviewed, English language, studies in U.S. only, Publish date: 2015-2023	147	141	8	8
Abortion and student health center	Peer-reviewed, English language, studies in U.S. only, Publish date: 2015-2023	2	2	1	1
College students and sexual health and religion	Peer-reviewed, English language, studies in U.S. only, Publish date: 2015-2023	52	50	1	2
College students and reproductive health services	Peer-reviewed, English language, studies in U.S. only, Publish date: 2015-2023	211	210	1	1
Quality abortion metrics	Peer-reviewed, English language, studies in U.S. only, Publish date: 2015-2023	22	19	4	3
Quality abortion indicators	Peer-reviewed, English language, studies in U.S. only, Publish date: 2015-2023	281	280	1	1

Appendix D

Table of Evidence for Literature Review

Database: Cumulative Index of Nursing and Allied Health Literature Search (CINAHL/EBSCO)

Search Terms	Limits	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
Abortion and students and colleges	Peer-reviewed, English language, studies in U.S. only, Publish date: 2015-2023	57	57	1	0
Abortion and student health center	Peer-reviewed, English language, studies in U.S. only, Publish date: 2015-2023	5	5	0	0
College students and sexual health and religion	Peer-reviewed, English language, studies in U.S. only, Publish date: 2015-2023	13	13	2	0
College students and reproductive health services	Peer-reviewed, English language, studies in U.S. only, Publish date: 2015-2023	10	10	0	0
Quality abortion metrics	Peer-reviewed, English language, studies in U.S. only, Publish date: 2015-2023	0	0	0	0
Quality abortion indicators	Peer-reviewed, English language, studies in U.S. only, Publish date: 2015-2023	0	0	0	0

Appendix E

Table of Evidence for Literature Review

Method: Hand searching

Two articles were found from scanning similar articles to the mesh terms applied. Two articles were found by scanning the references list of the articles included.

Appendix F

DNP Project Timeline

Date	Activities
February - April 2023	Conducted literature review on abortion quality metrics
May - July 2023	Worked with the SHC project team to finalize patient satisfaction surveys to be administered via telephone survey to patients seen from January through December 2023 Project Proposal Defense
August - September 2023	IRB approval obtained from CSUF and CSUN
September - December 2023	Data Collection
January - February 2024	Data Analysis
March 2024	Share results of data collection and analysis with the project team Determine the next plan of action based on results

Appendix G

Demographic characteristics of MAB patients (N=11)

Characteristic	<i>N</i>	%
Age range (years)		
17-18	2	18
19-20	2	18
21-22	4	36
23-24	1	9
≥25	2	18
Ethnicity		
Asian	3	27
Hispanic	5	45
African American	2	18
Caucasian	1	9
Academic Year		
Undergraduate	9	82
Graduate	2	18
Health insurance		
Yes	1	9
No	7	63
Family PACT	4	27
Gestational age (weeks)		
3-4	2	18
5-6	7	63
7-8	2	18
>8	0	0
Parity		
Nulliparous	11	100
Multiparous	0	0
Birth control method (pre-MAB)		
Yes	1	9
No	10	91

Note. Totals of percentages are not 100 for every characteristic because of rounding.

Appendix H

Outcome Measures of SHC MAB Services (N=9)

Outcome Measure	<i>n</i>	%
Abortion completion		
Complete	9	100
Incomplete	0	0
Failed	0	0
Hospitalized adverse events		
Yes	0	0
No	9	100
Birth control method (post-MAB)		
Yes	1	11
No	8	89

Note. Totals of percentages are not 100 for every characteristic because of rounding.

Appendix I

Proportion of MAB Patients and Abortion Completion (N=9)

Appendix J

Proportion of Hospitalized Adverse Related Events (N=9)

Appendix K

Proportion of MAB Patients who Adopted a Post-MAB Contraception (N=9)

Appendix L**Process Measures of SHC MAB Services (N=11)**

Process Measure 1	<i>average minutes</i>	%
Time spent with MAB provider		
Average time spent with MAB provider	85.8	97
Average total time spent in clinic	88.3	

Appendix M

Average Time Spent with MAB Provider (N=11)

Appendix N**Process Measures of SHC MAB Services (N=9)**

Process Measure 2	<i>N</i>	%
Patients who reported calling FoneMed		
Yes	0	0
No	9	100

Appendix O

Proportion of Patients who Reported Calling FoneMed (N=9)

Appendix P**Balancing Measures of SHC MAB Services (N=11)**

Balancing Measure	<i>N</i>	%
Unscheduled visits between initial MAB and MAB follow-up		
Yes	2	18
No	9	82

Appendix Q

Proportion of Unscheduled Visits between Initial MAB and MAB Follow-Up (N=11)

Appendix R

Chart Review Data Extraction Table

Patient Demographics Table

Age	
Race/Ethnicity	
Academic Year	
Health Insurance Coverage	
Gestational Age	
Parity	
Pre-MAB Contraception	

Outcome Measures

Outcome of MAB (Complete/ Incomplete/ Failed)	
Hospitalized Adverse Events Reported during MAB (Yes/No)	
Post-MAB Contraception	

Process Measures

Total Time Spent with MAB Provider/ Total Time Spent in Clinic (minutes)	
Reported Calling FoneMed (Yes/No)	

Balancing Measure

Unscheduled Visit in between MAB and post-MAB appt (Yes/No)	
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Appendix S

Medication Abortion Service Telephone Survey

- Survey is designed to assess the quality of the services we offer.
- Your responses will remain confidential.
- The information you share will have no impact on any future services you receive from us.
- You can decline to answer any of the questions.

1. How would you rate the overall care you received?

_____ Excellent _____ Good _____ Adequate _____ Poor

Comments:

2. Did the clinician provide information and/or answer your questions and concerns in a non-judgmental, respectful, and unbiased way? Yes _____ No _____

Comments:

3. Did the clinician use easy-to-understand words and phrases? Yes _____ No _____

Comments:

4. Did the clinician check with you to make sure you understood all the information provided? Yes _____ No _____

Comments:

5. Did the clinician explain possible complications related to the medication?

Yes _____ No _____

Comments:

6. We'd like to know if your pain medication was effective. Would you say it was:

Very effective _____ Somewhat effective _____ Not effective _____

Comments:

7. Is there anything else you'd like to share with us?

Comments:

Appendix T

Letter of Support

May 1, 2023

Kathleen Besas
Doctoral Candidate
School of Nursing
California State University, Fullerton

Dear Miss Besas,

As the Interim Director of the California State University, Northridge (CSUN) Klotz Student Health Center, I am pleased to support your Nursing Practice doctoral project on conducting a program evaluation of the clinic's medication abortion services. There are several access, socioeconomic, and psychosocial barriers that affect college women who seek abortion services. Existence of these barriers support the need for medication abortion services to be offered on our college campus, as outlined by the recent Senate Bill 24 mandate. Given this is a new service in California college student health centers, it is even more important to evaluate the program outcomes and overall quality in the provision of care. This will allow the Student Health Center to establish our understanding of the program's current status and identify areas where we can improve the service to ensure access to quality abortion care.

It is my hope that you will share your program evaluation outcomes with the Student Health Center Staff. We look forward to collaborating with you on this project and provide the support you need for its success.

Sincerely,

Ederlina P. Landeta

Ederlina (Lynne) P. Landeta, DNP
Interim Student Health Center Director
Work: (818) 677-3660
Email: lynne.landeta@csun.edu

Appendix U

CSUF IRB Approval

CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, FULLERTON

Office of Research and Sponsored Projects

P.O. Box 6850 or 1121 N. State College Blvd., 2nd Fl., Fullerton, CA 92831 / T 657-278-7719 / F 657-278-7238

APPROVAL NOTICE

*From the Institutional Review Board
California State University, Fullerton*

September 6, 2023

**From: Dr. Matt Englar-Carlson, Chair
CSUF Institutional Review Board**

To: PI: Kathleen Besas

Application No. HSR-23-24-43

Study Title: Evaluation of a Medication Abortion Program in a College Student Health Center

Re: Initial Exempt Review

The forms you submitted to this office regarding the use of human participants in the above-referenced proposal have been reviewed by the Regulatory Compliance Coordinator and the Chair of the California State University, Fullerton, Institutional Review Board. Your proposal is determined to be Category 4. Secondary research for which consent is not required; Secondary research uses of identifiable private information or identifiable biospecimens, if at least one of the following criteria is met:

- (i) The identifiable private information or identifiable biospecimens are publicly available;
- (ii) Information, which may include information about biospecimens, is recorded by the investigator in such a manner that the identity of the human subjects cannot readily be ascertained directly or through identifiers linked to the subjects, the investigator does not contact the subjects, and the investigator will not re-identify subjects;
- (iii) The research involves only information collection and analysis involving the investigator's use of identifiable health information when that use is regulated under 45 CFR parts 160 and 164, subparts A and E, for the purposes of "health care operations" or "research" as those terms are defined at 45 CFR 164.501 or for "public health activities and purposes" as described under 45 CFR 164.512(b); or
- (iv) The research is conducted by, or on behalf of, a Federal department or agency using government-generated or government-collected information obtained for nonresearch activities, if the research generates identifiable private information that is or will be maintained on information technology that is subject to and in compliance with section 208(b) of the E-Government Act of 2002, 44 U.S.C. 3501 note, if all of the identifiable private information collected, used, or generated as part of the activity will be maintained in systems of records subject to the Privacy Act of 1974, 5 U.S.C. 552a, and, if applicable, the information used in the research was collected subject to the Paperwork Reduction Act of 1995, 44 U.S.C. 3501 et seq.

The CSUF IRB has not evaluated your proposal for scientific merit, except to weigh the risk to the human participants and the aspects of the proposal related to potential risk and benefit. This approval notice does not replace any departmental or additional approvals which may be required.

In addition, all research personnel must follow the institutional safety guidelines outlined for CSUF's Presidential Directive 22. Additional information can be found in the [TITANS RETURN: COVID-19 Recovery website](#).

It is of utmost importance that you strictly adhere to the guidelines for human participants and that you follow the plan/methodology/procedures described in your research proposal. Since your proposal was determined to be exempt, there is no further review or annual renewal required by the CSUF IRB. **However, any change in protocol or consent form procedure requires re-submission to the CSUF IRB for approval prior to implementation.** Additionally, the principal investigator must promptly report, in writing, any unanticipated or adverse events causing risks to research participants or others.

Please be advised that if you are seeking external funding for this proposal, the above-reference title should match exactly with the title submitted to the funding sponsor. Any changes in project title should be submitted to the CSUF IRB prior to implementation.

By copy of this notice, the chair of your department (and/or co-investigator) is reminded that their responsibility for being informed concerning research projects involving human participants in the department, and should review all protocols of such investigations as often as needed to ensure that the project is being conducted in compliance with our institutional policies and with DHHS regulations.

The institution has an Assurance on file with the Office of Human Research Protections. The Assurance Number is FWA00015384.

Cc: IRB Office
Hannah Fraley

Appendix V

CSUN IRB Approval

The Committee for Protection of Human Subjects has approved the research referenced below. Please retain and use the IRB number on any correspondence related to the project.

Evaluation of a Medication Abortion Program in a College Student Health Center

Approval Date: September 28, 2023
Expiration Date: September 27, 2024
IRB Number: IRB-FY24-39
Principal Investigator: Kathleen Besas
Department: Student Health Center

Please retain this letter and information for your records. Please be aware that you must immediately report any change in research activity or amendments to any protocol associated with this study. You must also report any adverse events or unanticipated problems involving risks to subjects or others within one week of the time you are made aware of the problem. Please submit these reports via Cayuse IRB or email irb@csun.edu for assistance.

Please note that even though subject enrollment or involvement may be complete, if you are analyzing data with identifiable information, or if any link to identifiable information still exists, *you must renew your protocol*. In order to receive approval by the expiration date, please submit your renewal request at least 30 days prior to the expiration.

Important note: Please be aware that this approval means that you have met the requirements of federal regulations and CSUN policies governing human subjects research. Approval from other entities may also be needed. For example, access to data from private records (e.g. student, medical, or employment records, etc.) that are protected by FERPA, HIPAA, or other confidentiality policies requires permission from the holders of those records.

If Applicable: Some listservs and websites have policies regulating the types of advertisements or solicitations that can be posted, including from whom prior approval must be obtained before posting a recruitment notice for research. Similarly, most agencies, organizations, institutions, and even classroom instructors, have policies regarding who can solicit potential research participants from their students, employees, etc., what information must be included in solicitations, and how recruitment notices are distributed or posted. You should familiarize yourself with the external policies and approval procedures required of you to conduct your study. CSUN IRB approval or exemption does *not* substitute for these approvals or release you from the responsibility to insure that you have gained appropriate approvals *before* advertising your study or conducting your research. If you have any questions, please call the Research and Sponsored Programs department at (818) 677-2901 or email irb@csun.edu.

Sincerely,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read "K. Besas".

David Boyns, PhD
Chair, CSUN Committee for the Protection of Human Subjects

Review Type: Expedited
Funding: N/A
IRB Registration: IRB00001788
Assurance Number: FWA00001335